

New mixed complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) used as active substances in liquid membranes for ion-selective electrodes

Maria Pleniceanu*, Loan Burnea, Marian Isvoranu, Cezar Spinu and Elena Glodeanu

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, University of Craiova, 1100-Craiova, A. I. Cuza, 13, Romania

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Complexes of general formula $[M(NH_3)_2L]$, where M is Cu^{II} ion or Ni^{II} ion, and L is the ligand 2,3-dithio-6-nitrobenzochinoxalin-5,10-dione (dtnbqd), have been synthesised. These complexes have been used in practice for the achievement by two ion-selective electrodes with liquid membrane, for potentiometric determination of copper and nickel.

The present communication describes the synthesis¹ of mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with two different ligands, viz. NH_3 and 2,3-dithio-6-nitrobenzochinoxalin-5,10-dione (dtnbqd), the last one having been already used for the preparation of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} simple complexes².

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the mixed ligand complexes (Table 1) suggest a general formula $[M(NH_3)_2(dtnbqd)]$. This indicates copper and nickel in their oxidation state 2+, the dithiol as dianion, and NH_3 as neutral molecules in the complexes.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd.	M.p. °C	Colour	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$	Metal % :	
				Found	Calcd.
$[Cu(NH_3)_2L]$	228	Brown	19.3	15.52	15.31
$[Ni(NH_3)_2L]$	195	Orange	22.7	14.61	14.31

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, S and N analyses.

The electronic spectra of $[Cu(NH_3)_2L]$ displayed bands at 22800, 28000 and 34700 cm^{-1} assigned to transitions ${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ (*d-d*), ${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ (*d-d*) and ${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_u$ (CT). $[Ni(NH_3)_2L]$ showed bands at 22200, 31200 and 38300 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ (*d-d*), ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ (*d-d*) and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_u$ (CT) transitions.

The bands displayed in the spectra of these mixed

ligand complexes are also present in the spectra of the simple complexes $[Cu(dtnbqd)_2]^{2-}$ and $[Ni(dtnbqd)_2]^{2-}$ having square-planar structure² and this confirms the same structure for the present complexes too. The increase in intensity of the absorption bands in the electronic spectra of the mixed ligand complexes $[Cu(NH_3)_2(dtnbqd)]$ and $[Ni(NH_3)_2(dtnbqd)]$ is attributed to the absorption of the ammonia molecules.

The characteristic ir bands for the ligand and complexes are presented in Table 2.

The literature reports the coordination of the 2,3-dithio-6-nitrobenzochinoxalin-5,10-dione to Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} through the two sulphur atoms of the SH groups (which are in *ortho*-position) of the ligand. In the mixed ligand complexes new characteristic bands due to the N-H bond vibrations from the NH_3 molecule are observed which are absent in the spectra of the simple complexes. It is also noticed that the modification of the position and intensity of the C-S ligand bands in the ir spectra of the complexes is another proof of dithiol coordination through sulphur atoms of the SH groups, which are in *ortho*-position in the molecule of this bidentate ligand.

Thus in the complexes the dithiol acts as dianion and two ammonia molecules act as neutral molecules coordinated to the central metal ions.

The complexes being insoluble in water and soluble in nitrobenzene, were used for achievement of two ion-selective electrodes for potentiometric determination of copper and nickel⁴.

Table 2. Ir spectral data (cm^{-1}) of the complexes

Compd.	vNH	vSH	vC=C	vC-N		vC=O	vNO ₂		γ ₂ CH	γ ₄ CH	vC-s
				VC=N	def.		asym.	sym			
dtnbqd	-	2325	1200 1405	1265	1025	1650	1530	1365	rocking	rocking	690
$[Cu(NH_3)_2L]$	3490	2300	1135 1465	1200	1045	1700	1520	1350	820	765	695
$[Ni(NH_3)_2L]$	3475	2315	1140 1470	1210	1055	1645	1545	1350	840	780	705

Experimental

CuCl_2 anhydrous and $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H.), 2,3-dithio-6-nitrobenzochinoxalin-5,10-dione (recrystallized), 25% NH_3 solution, absolute ethanol and ethyl ether were used.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Zeiss-Jena Specord IR-75 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Zeiss-Jena spectrophotometer. Molar conductivity was determined using a Radelkis OK-102 instrument.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{dtnbqd})]$: CuCl_2 (1 g) was dissolved in excess of 25% NH_3 solution until the solution became intense blue, corresponding to $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ complex formation. To it was added in small portion under continuous stirring and heating, a solution of the ligand (2.5 g) in a minimum quantity of dimethylformamide. The resulting brown microcrystalline solid was allowed to settle for 24 h, then washed with absolute ethanol and ethyl ether and vacuum-dried.

$[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{dtnbqd})]$: To the solution obtained by dis-

solving $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g) in excess of 25% NH_3 solution (until the solution became intense blue) was added in small portion under continuous stirring and heating a solution of dithiol (2 g) in minimum quantity of dimethylformamide. The formed dark orange crystalline solid was allowed to settle for 24 h at the room temperature, then washed with distilled water, absolute ethanol and ethyl ether and vacuum-dried.

References

1. M. Pleniceanu, Doctoral Thesis, Inst. Politehnic Bucuresti, 1986.
2. N. Muresan, L. S. Muresan and V. Muresan, *Anal. Univ. Craiova, Ser. Chim.*, 1993, **21**, 22; V. Muresan, L. S. Muresan, A. Reiss and N. Muresan, *Anal. Univ. Craiova, Ser. Chim.*, 1993, **21**, 28; N. Muresan and V. Muresan, 'National Conference of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering', Bucuresti, 1993, Vol. 1, p. 49.
3. N. Muresan, Doctoral Thesis, Inst. Politehnic Bucuresti, 1975.
4. M. Pleniceanu, M. Preda, N. Muresan and C. Spinu, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1997, **134**, 177.